

NAMES OF SAINTS, PROTECTING PEOPLE FROM DISEASES AND HEALTH PROBLEMS, LATIN BY ORIGIN

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Abstract

The research object of the present text is the names of saints, protecting people from diseases and health problems, and which are Latin by origin. The observation is implemented on the corpus of 41 names of saints and their variants, 29 of which are masculine by gender, and 12 are feminine.

These names are classified in several major groups in accordance to the type of disease and health problem, i. e. a thematical group, and in accordance to the type of the appellative as a part of speech and the principles of derivation used in the process of coining the examined anthroponyms.

Keywords: *names of saints, to protect, diseases, health problems, corpus.*

The research object of the present text is the names of saints, protecting people from diseases and health problems, and which are Latin by origin.

The observation is implemented on the corpus of forty-one names of saints and their variants, twenty-nine of which are masculine by gender, and twelve are feminine. As a main source of information about the basic classification in accordance to the type of disease and health problem, whose name is with a Latin origin, is used the Russian site <http://kurufin.ru/>. They are also classified according to the type of the appellative as a part of speech, used in the process of their forming, i. e. if it is a noun, adjective, etc., and to the principles of derivation, i. e. if the name is coined from the form for Nom. sg. of the appellative or from its working base. In order the information, presented in these classifications, to be complete, some additional sources are also used and their complete list is given in *References*.

1. Names of saints classification in accordance to the diseases and health problems

1.1. Masculine names of saints protecting people from diseases and health problems

There are masculine names of saints protecting people from all the diseases or health problems. For example, *Maurus*.

But there are masculine names of saints protecting people only from one or some diseases or health problems:

(1) from alcoholism: *Bonefatius/Bonifacius, Urbanus*;

(2) from podagra: *Maurus*;

(3) from plague: *Sebastianus, Valentinus*;

(4) from cancer: *Peregrinus*;

(5) from AIDS: *Peregrinus*;

(6) from fever: *Claudius/Clodius, Cornelius*;

(7) from hernia: *Albanus*;

- (8) from calculi in ren/rens: **Benedictus**;
- (9) from calculi and sand in ren/rens: **Albanus**;
- (10) from lombargo: **Laurentius**;
- (11) from infertility: **Antonius**;
- (12) from toothache: **Caius/Cajus/Gaius**;
- (13) from drug addiction: **Maximilian**;
- (14) from faints: **Urbanus, Valentinus**;
- (15) from spasms, convulsions: **Mauricius/Mauritius**;
- (16) from intoxication: **Amabilis, Benedictus**;
 - (a) for example, from the intoxication caused by snake-biting: **Amabilis, Hilarius, Patricius/Patritius, Vitus**;
- (17) from eye diseases: **Augustinus, Felix, Laurentius, Longinus**;
 - (a) for example, from myopia: **Clarus**;
- (18) from mental diseases: **Amabilis**;
 - (a) for example, from epilepsy: **Albanus, Cornelius, Sebastianus, Valentinus, Vitus**;
- (19) from skin diseases: **Benedictus, Peregrinus**;
 - (a) wounds, ulcers: **Peregrinus**;
 - (b) eczemas: **Antonius**;
- (20) from ear diseases: **Cornelius**;
 - (a) for example, from deafness: **Franciscus**;
- (21) from gastrointestinal problems: **Bonaventura**;
- (22) from infectious diseases: **Sebastianus**;
- (23) from throat problems:
 - (a) sore throat: **Blasius**;
 - (b) cough: **Quintinus**;
 - (c) pertussis: **Blasius**;
 - (d) choking caused by bone in the throat: **Blasius**;
 - (e) hoarseness: **Maurus**.

1.2. Masculine names of saints protecting people from different kinds of epidemics

There are masculine names of saints protecting people from different kinds of epidemics, for example, **Agricola**.

1.3. Feminine names of saints protecting people from diseases and health problems

There are feminine names of saints protecting people from all the diseases or health problems. For example, **Iuliana/Juliana**.

But there are feminine names of saints protecting people only from one or some diseases or health problems:

- (1) from fever: **Petronilla**;
- (2) from headache: **Bibiana/Viviana**;
- (3) from infertility: **Felicitas**;
- (4) from dysentery: **Lucia**;

- (5) from bleeding: *Lucia*;
- (6) from sleepwalking: *Christina*;
- (7) from hangover: *Bibiana/Viviana*;
- (8) from mental diseases: *Bibiana/Viviana, Christina*;
- (a) for example, from epilepsy: *Bibiana/Viviana*;
- (9) from eye diseases: *Clara, Lucia*;
- (a) for example, from blindness: *Lucia*.

1.4. Feminine names of saints protecting pregnant women

There are feminine names of saints protecting pregnant women, for example *Silvia*.

1.5. Feminine names of saints protecting from infant spasms, convulsions or mortality

There are feminine names of saints protecting from infant spasms, convulsions or mortality, for example *Scholastica, Iulitta/Julitta, Nona/Nonna, Felicitas, Francisca*.

2. Names of saints classification according to derivation models or etymology

According to derivation there are:

- (a) masculine names derived from a noun: *Agricola* (< *agricola* – “farmer”¹), *Augustinus* (< *Augustus* (< *augustus* – “great”²), *Clarus* (< *Clara*³), *Laurentius* (< *Laurentum* – a name of a town in Ancient Italy⁴), *Peregrinus* (< *peregrinus* – “traveler, pilgrim”⁵);
- (b) feminine names derived from a noun: *Bibiana/Viviana* (< *Bibianus/Vivianus* (< *vivus* – “alive”), *Christina* (< *Christinus* (< *christianus* – “Christian”), *Felicitas* (< *felicitas* – “happiness”), *Francisca* (< *Franciscus*), *Iuliana/Juliana* (< *Iulianus/Julianus* (< *Iulius/Julius* < *ιουλος* – “curly”), *Iulitta/Julitta* (< *Iulia/Julia* (< *Iulius/Julius*), *Lucia* (< *Lucius* (< *lux* – “light”), *Petronilla* (< *Petronius* (< *petro* – “yokel, bumpkin” or from *πέτρα* *πέτρος* – “stone, rock”), *Scholastica* (< *scholasticus* – “rhetorician”);
- (c) masculine names derived from an adjective: *Albanus* (< *Albanus* – “from Alba”⁶), *Amabilis* (< *amabilis* – “kind, amiable”⁷), *Claudius/Clodius* (< *claudus* – „lame”⁸), *Felix* (< *felix* – “lucky, happy”⁹), *Franciscus* (< *Franciscus* – “Frenchman”¹⁰), *Hilarius* (< *hilaris* – “merry”¹¹), *Longinus* (< *longus* – “long”¹²), *Patricius/Patritius* (< *patricius* – “noble”¹³), *Quintinus* (< *Quintus* (< *quintus* – “fifth”¹⁴), *Sebastianus* (< *Sebastianus* – “from *Sebastus*”¹⁵), *Urbanus* (< *urbanus* – “city”¹⁶);
- (d) feminine names derived from an adjective: *Clara* (< *clara* – “clear, bright”);
- (e) masculine names derived from a participle: *Valentinus* (< *valens* – “strong, sound, vivid”¹⁷);
- (f) masculine names derived from a combination between an adjective and a noun: *Bonaventura* (< *bona* – “good” and *ventura* – “chance,

- fate*¹⁸), *Bonefatius/Bonifacius* (< *bonum* – “good” and *fatum* – “destiny”¹⁹);
- (j) masculine or feminine names derived from the form for Nom. sg. of the Latin appellative: *Agricola, Albanus, Amabilis, Bonaventura, Felix, Franciscus, Hilarius, Patricius/Patritius, Peregrinus, Sebastianus, Urbanus, Clara, Felicitas*;
- (h) masculine or feminine names derived from the working base, i. e. the form for Gen. sg. without the case ending, of the Latin appellative: *Augustinus, Bonefatius/Bonifacius, Clarus, Claudius/Clodius, Laurentius, Longinus, Quintinus, Valentinus, Vitus, Bibiana/Viviana, Christina, Francisca, Iuliana/Juliana, Iulitta/Julitta, Lucia, Petronilla, Scholastica*.

According to etymology there are:

- (a) masculine or feminine names with more than one etymology: *Antonius* (with an Etruscan origin with unknown meaning or with a Greek origin, derived from *ανθος* – “flower”²⁰ or from *αντέω* (<*αντάω* < *αντιάω* – “take part”²¹), *Benedictus* (< *benedictus* – “blessed”²² or from *benedico* – “talk good things about someone”²³), *Blasius* (< *blaesus* – “mumbling”²⁴, from *blatio* – “babble”²⁵ or from the Greek *βλάσιος* – “bowlegged”²⁶), *Cornelius* (< *cornu* – “horn”²⁷ or from *cornum* – “strawberry”²⁸), *Mauricius/Mauritius* (< *Maurus*²⁹ or from *mauricius* – “Moorish”³⁰), *Maurus* (< *maurus* – “dark-skinned”³¹ or from *mauricius* – “Moorish”³²), *Maximilianus* (< *Maximus* (< *maximus* – “big; great”³³) or from combination between the names *Maximus* and *Aemilianus* (< *Aemilius* < *aemulus* – “enemy”³⁴), *Vitus* (< *vita* – “life”³⁵ or from *via* – “way, road”³⁶), *Nona/Nonna* (< *nonus* – “ninth” or from *nonna* – “nun”), *Silvia* (< *Silvius* (< *silva* – “forest”) or directly from *silva* – “forest”).
- (b) masculine or feminine names with unknown etymology, for example *Caius/Cajus/Gaius*³⁷.

The examined names are canonized only by the Catholic Church (*Agricola, Albanus, Amabilis, Bonaventura, Clarus, Franciscus, Peregrinus, Quintinus; Bibiana/Viviana, Clara, Scholastica*), or by the both Churches, the Catholic and the Orthodox one (*Antonius, Augustinus, Benedictus, Blasius, Bonefatius/Bonifacius, Caius/Cajus/Gaius, Claudius/Clodius, Cornelius, Felix, Hilarius, Laurentius, Longinus, Mauricius/Mauritius, Maurus, Maximilianus, Patricius/Patritius, Sebastianus, Urbanus, Valentinus, Vitus; Christina, Felicitas, Francisca, Iuliana/Juliana, Iulitta/Julitta, Lucia, Nona/Nonna, Petronilla, Silvia*).

The bigger part of the masculine names is derived from an adjective, while the bigger part of the feminine ones is derived from nouns (and in almost all of the cases from a masculine proper name, which is a typical model for coining a female proper name in the Latin anthroponomical system).

In most of the cases masculine by gender names are derived from the form for Nom. sg. of the appellative used as a basis in the name-forming process, while just the opposite is true for the feminine names.

The bigger part of the observed masculine and feminine names of saints is canonized by the both Churches, the Catholic and the Orthodox one.

Notes

¹Petrovsky, 1966.

²Knappová, 1985, <http://kurufin.ru/>

³www.behindthename.com, <http://kurufin.ru/>

⁴Dzyatkovskaya *et alii*, 1986, Ilchev, 1959, Knappová, 1985, Petrovsky, 1966, www.behindthename.com, <http://kurufin.ru/>

⁵Knappová, 1985, Petrovsky, 1966, www.behindthename.com, <http://kurufin.ru/>

⁶Knappová, 1985, www.behindthename.com, <http://kurufin.ru/>

⁷www.behindthename.com, <http://kurufin.ru/>

⁸Doichinovich, 2010, Dzyatkovskaya *et alii*, 1986, Knappová, 1985, Kol *et alii*, 2011, Petrovsky, 1966, www.behindthename.com, <http://kurufin.ru/>, www.leksykony.interia.pl

⁹Dzyatkovskaya *et alii*, 1986, Knappová, 1985, Petrovsky, 1966, www.behindthename.com, <http://kurufin.ru/>, www.leksykony.interia.pl

¹⁰Ilchev, 1959, www.behindthename.com, <http://kurufin.ru/>

¹¹Dzyatkovskaya *et alii*, 1986, Ilchev, 1959, Knappová, 1985, Petrovsky, 1966, www.behindthename.com, www.leksykony.interia.pl

¹²Dzyatkovskaya *et alii*, 1986, Ilchev, 1959, www.behindthename.com, <http://kurufin.ru/>, www.leksykony.interia.pl

¹³Knappová, 1985, Petrovsky, 1966, www.behindthename.com, www.ksiegaimion.com, <http://kurufin.ru/>, www.leksykony.interia.pl

¹⁴www.behindthename.com, <http://kurufin.ru/>

¹⁵Knappová, 1985, Petrovsky, 1966, www.behindthename.com, <http://kurufin.ru/>

¹⁶Knappová, 1985, Petrovsky, 1966, www.behindthename.com, <http://kurufin.ru/>, www.leksykony.interia.pl

¹⁷Doichinovich, 2010, Ilchev, 1959, Knappová, 1985, Kol *et alii*, 2011, www.behindthename.com, <http://kurufin.ru/>

¹⁸<http://kurufin.ru/>, www.leksykony.interia.pl

¹⁹Dzyatkovskaya *et alii*, 1986, www.behindthename.com, www.leksykony.interia.pl

²⁰Ilchev, 1959, <http://kurufin.ru/>

²¹Dzyatkovskaya *et alii*, 1986, Kol *et alii*, 2011.

²²Dzyatkovskaya *et alii*, 1986, Ilchev, 1959, Knappová, 1985, Petrovsky, 1966, www.behindthename.com, <http://kurufin.ru/>, www.leksykony.interia.pl

²³www.leksykony.interia.pl

²⁴www.behindthename.com, <http://kurufin.ru/>

²⁵www.leksykony.interia.pl

²⁶Dzyatkovskaya *et alii*, 1986, www.behindthename.com, <http://kurufin.ru/>

²⁷Doichinovich, 2010, Dzyatkovskaya *et alii*, 1986, Knappová, 1985, Petrovsky, 1966, www.behindthename.com, <http://kurufin.ru/>, www.leksykony.interia.pl

²⁸Dzyatkovskaya *et alii*, 1986; Petrovsky, 1966.

²⁹Knappová, 1985, www.behindthename.com, <http://kurufin.ru/>

³⁰Garkovich, 1966, <http://kurufin.ru/>

³¹www.behindthename.com

³²Dzyatkovskaya *et alii*, 1986, Knappová, 1985, <http://kurufin.ru/>

³³Dzyatkovskaya *et alii*, 1986, www.behindthename.com, <http://kurufin.ru/>

³⁴Dzyatkovskaya *et alii*, 1986, Knappová, 1985, Kol *et alii*, 2011, www.leksykony.interia.pl

³⁵Doichinovich, 2010, Kol *et alii*, 2011, www.behindthename.com, <http://kurufin.ru/>

³⁶Knappová, 1985, Kol *et alii*, 2011.

³⁷www.behindthename.com, <http://kurufin.ru/>

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